

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGES

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Abstract: Language is the most important means of communication between people. Created in the process of social development and universally human express interest. Origin and development of language. It is strongly associated with human society. language is the history of mankind is as old as. A nation is a complex made up of a confederation of sister tribes. Territory, culture and spirituality are the totality of the environment. National languages, one of the main symbols of the people, are mutually as an independent major economic and cultural central language is displayed.

Key words: language, changes, formation, developments, society, nation, humans.

The question of language origin has occupied mankind since ancient times is interesting. Language development is very complex. It's not just about linguistics, it's about many other fields. Science such as anthropology, psychology, and ethnography is the subject of research where it appeared, how many languages were there in the beginning, this language or that language. Structures and similar questions are still scientifically sound. I didn't find a perfect answer. According to some scientists, language is appeared about 500,000 years ago. It is well known that language, like any other thing or event, is subject to change.

What will language change in 500,000 years? Imagine what happened, it's scientific and practical. It is impossible to learn from a theoretical point of view. Language for us, the state of development before the appearance of writing it's dark we are only writing in the aftermath based on written records of language development, we can think But writing is the learning of a language, the emergence of a language. The question of existence cannot be fully elucidated. Nevertheless, some scientists have their own take on the matter, commented.

How Ancient Greek Philosophers Became Controversial. They had a long and heated discussion about its release. History has shown that Greek philosophers contradicted each other on this issue. There is no relationship between names and things, these are names it is a language because it was created by people who speak that language. They put forward the idea that it is an artifact. this is a group scientists are called anomalies. Plato is the leader of another group scientists say there is a certain relationship between an object and its name. Connections are caused by the properties and properties of things, "This connection was made by the power of God." Historically, this flow was called analogue.

Language is created in human society as a means of communication. It is a social phenomenon to serve. Its social nature is different it manifests itself as a service to society rather than to the individual. All languages emerged in the course of human historical development. Representing cultural and scientific wealth, passed down from generation to generation. It is the most important means of heredity. The main thing that distinguishes language from other

social phenomena. Its peculiarity is that language is all the activity of society. I am in charge of the fields. It is the historical development of human society as a concrete historical norm created in the process. Basic communication to serve all members equally tool, so the language is not class based. Speakers use language created by human communities. Follow the laws of that language. at the same time. Side by side, all the speakers, especially the writer, the scientist, his speech a particular contribution to the development of language in the course of his work you add Humans communicate and think differently than language.

Language is the entire history of human society over the centuries society as a whole, not specific groups. It is a social phenomenon formed by members of society. At the same time, language belongs to a particular era, to a particular socioeconomic era in the course of the history of society as a whole, not the product of society a product of several eras of various classes of society always represent it. There is no language for only one class or her one group. Language is therefore a group- and caste-independent whole serve society. Language is an important means of expression. speak thoughtfully. Relationships are complex processes. Language exists as an expression of its own thoughts. Thinking is a complex process carried out based on language. Both thinking and work processes in individual societies.

Language is a social phenomenon. Language arises in the process of social development. The language is not a natural biological phenomenon. Its development does not follow the laws of nature. Language is society as a whole universal throughout history as a product of progressive times provide interest.

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